

EFCF_A1209

Advancement on Fuel and Operation Mode Flexible Solid Oxide Cell Stacks and Modules

Antonio Alfano, Jouni Puranen, Valtteri Pulkkinen, Matti Noponen

Elcogen, Niittyvillankuja 4, 01510 Vantaa/Finland;

Tel. (Finland): +358-10-323-3060

finland@elcogen.com

Abstract

A key advantage of solid oxide (SO) technology is its flexibility on the type of operating fuel and operating mode, being it either fuel cell (FC) electrolysis (EL) or reversible operation (rSOC). Particularly, SOE operation is rapidly emerging as a key enabler of the transition to a hydrogen economy reliant on clean H₂ production routes, thanks to its higher efficiency and lower operation costs compared to competing technologies.

In both scenarios, Elcogen is positioned at the forefront of this field with demonstrated gross electrical efficiency of 75.3% in FC mode operation with NG and specific energy consumption (SEC) of 33 kWh/kg for hydrogen production in EL mode.

Demonstrating the capability to operate with multiple fuels has the intrinsic advantage of opening up the field of application where SOFC can be employed. A prominent example is the maritime industry. Elcogen is actively involved in this field within the FuelSOME project, funded under Horizon Europe program. Aim is to elucidate the influence of non-conventional fuels on different levels, to develop modules to scale up the power range and, eventually, to the impact on system design and operation. Such fuels include ammonia (NH₃) and methanol (MeOH). Results will be discussed keeping an eye on stacks and module development, allowing to target high power range applications.

Similar goal is pursued within SO-FREE. Elcogen activities in this project, funded under Horizon Europe program, aim at developing a multi-stack module while establishing a standardized interface to the system and benchmark the performances of stacks and system under various fuel blends. Such approach will result, together with the project partners effort, in facilitating the uptake of SO technology.

Elcogen is actively engaged in activities connected to the development of large scale of stacks for EL operation. Such activities are performed within the OUTFOX project, funded under Horizon Europe program, which aims at removing scale as a limiting factor for the widespread adoption of SOEL for clean hydrogen production. Activities at stack level will target a 70% increase in current density compared to the current state of the art and improvement of degradation level. In parallel, through modelling and simulation, a new concept will be devised where larger cells can be used. This will target the realization of a new stack which will be specifically tailored for large capacity installations of solid oxide electrolysis systems.

Introduction

The growing awareness around Solid Oxide (SO) technology as a key enabler of a sustainable energy transition calls for an increase in readiness level to support the deployment of systems based on SO stacks and modules at scale. This applies to both fuel cell (FC) and electrolysis (EL) operation, where higher efficiency and lower operating costs respectively are key in promoting their market adoption for sustainable power generation and clean hydrogen production.

Elcogen core technology items cover from development and manufacturing of electrochemical cells, stacks and modules. As the field of application grows, the R&D efforts need to be aligned to support the market needs. Specifically, this requires manufacturing products with high yield, efficiency and lifetime. Flexibility must at the same time be ensured, in order to fulfill the needs for both operating modes as well as reversible systems (rSOC). This requires in particular to ensure that the expected performances are preserved regardless of the type of fuel used, operating conditions and installation size.

In this regard, Elcogen is committed to developing its products family to meet such needs, with efforts deployed on multiple levels, from laboratory testing up to small scale installations. In this paper, an overview of the development approach on stacks and modules level will be presented, with particular emphasis on the capabilities of Elcogen stacks to handle harsh conditions in both FC and EL mode, delivering beyond state-of-the-art performances with respect to tolerance against exotic fuels and high operating current density for H₂ production. Such development activities are contextualized within relevant projects funded by the European Commission, highlighting Elcogen commitment in fostering a robust network around SO field.

1. Technology Development Approach

Elcogen stacks and modules come in different sizes, enabling flexibility in testing while still ensuring reproducible results are generated at all levels. In this section, a description of the research approach employed is provided, with a focus on the various scales of testing as exemplified in Figure 1.

1.1 Short Stacks

The elcoStack® E350 is the best suited platform for explorative R&D tests. Consisting of 15 single repeating units (SRU), its power level, flow rates and geometrical footprint fits seamlessly in the majority of the test platform with little to none customization. By employing the same core design (with the only exception of the air manifolding concept) of the commercial product, the elcoStack® E3000, it ensures full transferability of the results to the full-scale stacks. The low amount of components required to assemble such stacks enable a fast implementation of demanding R&D concepts, from components and materials testing to exotic fuels and demanding operating conditions.

In the technology development, the elcoStack® E350 is the first go-to platform to study the response of the stack and its components beyond the standard operating conditions. Here, stress tests are performed with the aim of identifying the critical threshold which triggers the stack degradation and/or components failure. By careful design of experiments (DoE), the stack response to harsh operating conditions are mapped, allowing to identify the safe boundaries within which the full scale stacks can be operated. At the same time, explorative

campaigns can be designed with the goal of mapping the expected performance of the full scale stacks. This allows fast iterations and the collection of relevant information which can aid the development of system operation and control logics for degradation mitigation in relevant operating conditions.

1.2 Full Stacks

Based on the learnings derived from the short stack tests, relevant operating conditions can be defined for testing of the full scale, commercial stack platform of the elcoStack® E3000. Consisting of 119 SRU, this stack can be customized up to including full level of instrumentation, allowing thus to measure the voltage of each individual layer.

This platform allows to directly draw information from the core product which, eventually, will be used at system level. Here, metrics such as efficiency and degradation can be calculated based on the operation window defined at short stack level.

Long term testing campaigns in controlled laboratory environment enable to carefully screen and assess the stack performances, allowing to gather relevant information on the expected behavior of stack when integrated in multi-stack units. This results in valuable information which aids the development of operation logics at system scale.

At the same time, components and materials tested at short stack can be here fully validated, quantifying gains in terms of performances and/or cost against the standard product.

The large number of layers provides a first understanding of components reliability, yield and reproducibility to support risk assessment during product upgrades.

1.3 Modules

The stack module represents the last link of the chain, where stack performances are assessed in system relevant environment. Thanks to the modularity of the elcoModule®, it is possible to couple 2, 4 or more elcoStack® E3000 with structural elements closely derived from real field uses.

This platform bridges laboratory testing with system integration, where interaction of the stack with its surroundings becomes paramount.

The module indeed often represents the direct interface between the stack and the system and its balance of plants (BoP) components. By analyzing the stack behavior in such environments and comparing it with the large scale stack tests, it is possible to draw conclusions which aim at highlighting the focus elements which require attention while operating the stacks outside of a controlled laboratory environment. This allows both to redefine relevant control strategies as well as identify suitable level of instrumentation to monitor the stack performance in a context where instrumentation level might be necessarily reduced.

Stack modules also offer a relevant stage where stack-to-stack performance variation can be assessed, and expected results from modelling work on e.g. temperature, flow distribution can be validated. This offers valuable information on defining real-life stack operation window which can take into account modularity weak spots which can result in operating the stack in harsh conditions.

At the same time, as the number of stacks grows, so does the number of components, further building up confidence on components robustness.

Figure 1 Schematic of multilevel approach for stack and module development for fuel and operation flexibility

2. Projects Overview

Public projects offer a great opportunity of bringing together expertise from various fields to jointly contribute to reach a common goal. Elcogen is actively involved in 15+ projects which support internal development activities, aiming at pushing the boundaries of our state-of-the-art products. Below, three notable examples which highlight the flexibility and robustness of Elcogen products and are aligned with the strategic development anticipated by the markets.

2.1 FuelSOME

FuelSOME (Grant Agreement – 101069828, funded by European Union) focuses on establishing the technological feasibility of a flexible, scalable, and multi-fuel capable energy generation system based on Solid Oxide Fuel Cells (SOFC) technology specially catered for long-distance maritime shipping. This sector needs to focus on the sustainable supply of alternative fuels such as Ammonia, Methanol and Hydrogen at scale and to develop highly-efficient multifuel energy conversion systems. Ammonia and methanol being liquid fuels have high volumetric energy density and are also the most promising candidate fuels for decarbonized deep-sea shipping.

The project revolves around 5 key objectives, two of which are strongly bound to technological advancement at stack and stack module level. Those are the commitment to undertake research at the stack level to boost performances, efficiency lifetime and tolerance limits while developing a modularized solution for validation (Key Objective 2) and to design, build and test a lab scale prototype of the multi-fuel energy generator based on SOFC technology (Key Objective 3).

Within this project, Elcogen aims at exploring the boundaries of the stack capabilities and gain valuable insights by developing a 6 kW stack module capable of operating with high efficiency and reliability under fuel flexible conditions.

2.2 SO-FREE

The SO-FREE Project (Grant Agreement 101006667, funded by European Union and Fuel Cell and Hydrogen Joint Undertaking) aims at developing a SOFC-based system for combined heat and power (CHP) generation. This means a versatile system concept for efficient, near-zero-emission, fuel-flexible and truly modular power and heat supply to end users in the residential, commercial and municipal sectors.

Notably, the SO-FREE consortium will strive to realize a standardized stack module system interface. This interface design will be taken to the International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC) as a new work item proposal (NWIP) for international standardization. In such a way commercial barriers to full and free competition between SOFC stack suppliers and system integrators aim to be levelled.

Within this project, Elcogen will contribute with advancements on a 6 kW stack module, which interfaces will be tailored and aligned with needs for the definition of such standardized platform. Additionally, stack performances with H₂, natural gas and blends will be evaluated first at short stack level [1], allowing to map their performance and designing operation strategies for further operation of the 5 kW prototype system.

2.3 OUTFOX

The OUTFOX Project (Grant Agreement 101101439, funded by European Union and Fuel Cell and Hydrogen Joint Undertaking) aims at strengthening the EU's position within the green industrial landscape by fostering the continent's innovation ecosystem around low-cost renewable hydrogen. The ambition is to remove scale as a limiting factor for SO technology to contribute as an energy efficient, low cost solution for hydrogen production. The methodology revolves around developing and validating upscaled cells, larger stacks, and their assembly into enlarged modules, as well as designing the integration of these enlarged pieces into a multi-MW scale electrolysis unit. It builds around a robust and well-structured consortium which brings together key stakeholders through the whole value chain, from unit cell manufacturers to system integrators and end users, strongly supported by research centers in charge of testing and evaluation of the concept.

Within this project, Elcogen will undertake actions aimed both as developing a new stack concept specifically targeted for high volume H₂ production, and at the same time carry out activities aimed at increasing the current density up to 0.85 A/cm², starting from short stack testing up to 80 kW demonstration together with project partners.

3. Results

In this section, specific emphasis will be paid to the latest advancements in terms of stack performances in both FC and EL mode. Each example will provide insights on the type of data collected and their specific value for further stages of testing and development.

3.1 NH₃ Slip Tolerance

As part of FuelSOME project, one crucial point is understanding the robustness of the stack against exposure to uncracked ammonia which could, for example, reach the stack due to incomplete cracking in the fuel processing unit.

Pure ammonia is known to pose serious hazards to the integrity of stack components, potentially leading to accelerated degradation or, in extreme cases, early failures [2][3].

On the other hand, strict requirements on the fuel processing unit increase significantly the energy consumption with negative impacts on the overall system efficiency.

Therefore, understanding the tolerance of the stack against possible residuals of NH₃ in the fuel stream greatly simplifies the system operation strategy with overall benefits from reduced complexity and efficiency gain point of view, together with enhanced robustness of the overall system against accidental out-of-specs operation.

To this extent, a dedicated test was carried out on an elcoStack® E350. The aim of the test was evaluating the stack response to subsequent increase of NH₃ slip. Overall, the test consisted of 8 phases, as depicted in Figure 2. The gas composition of each section is reported in Table 1. For each phase the stack was kept for at least 150 hours under nominal loading conditions (NOC - Current = 30 A, Fuel Utilization 60%, Air Utilization 22.5 %). In between each phase, open circuit voltage (OCV) was recorded using the gas composition used in Section 1.

Section 0 served as baselining phase, to characterize the stack performances using a blend of 50:50 H₂:N₂. In sections 1 to 7, the H₂:N₂ ratio is adjusted through mass flow controllers to represent cracked ammonia composition. Sections 1 and 7 represent a 100% cracked scenario (0% NH₃ slip). In sections 2 to 6, the NH₃ slip is increased up to 15%. H₂:N₂ ratio is adjusted to keep the fuel utilization (FU) constant and equal to 60% (assuming 100% cracking inside the stack).

Average cell voltage under NOC is reported in Table 1, together with the OCV recorded before the transition to the next test section.

Figure 2 Overview of the average cell voltage of an elcoStack® E350 under ammonia exposure. Color coding and numbers identify different gas compositions as described in Table 1. Gas inlet temperature: 640°C

The data, summarized in Table 1, allow us to draw insightful conclusions on the stack response after being exposed to increasing amount of NH₃.

When looking at the NOC voltage and OCV, two distinct effects can be noticed.

First, NOC voltage slightly decreased upon increasing NH₃ slip. Provided that the nominal FU remains constant, this effect can be ascribed to the increased fraction of internal cracking. Due to the heat absorbed by the reaction, a local decrease in temperature can be expected. This in turn affects the voltage output.

On the other hand, the OCV measured under reference conditions after each section (composition as per section 1) points out to a non-negligible drop particularly after 15% NH₃ slip. This could indicate an increase in internal leakages and an accelerated deterioration. Further analysis will be performed through post test characterization of stack components.

The column “Risk” in Table 1 visually summarizes the likelihood of incurring in deviations from expected lifetime/degradation, with green being low (no deviations), yellow indicating medium (possible effect on degradation) and darker shades progressively higher risk, with section 6 potentially leading to early failure.

Interestingly, section 7 hints to a possible stabilization, suggesting that the effect of exposure is mitigated once the slip is decreased.

Table 1 Summary of relevant parameters during the NH₃ exposure test. *OCV is always measured with gas composition 1

Section #	NOC [mV]	NH ₃ [%]	H ₂ [I _N /min]	N ₂ [I _N /min]	OCV* [mV]	Risk
0	923.1	0	7.84	7.84	1212	Green
1	907.5	0	5.23	1.74	1190	Green
2	906.1	1	5.10	1.70	1189	Green
3	904.7	2.5	4.97	1.66	1189	Green
4	903.6	5	4.23	1.57	1188.7	Yellow
5	901	10	4.28	1.42	1184.4	Orange
6	898.2	15	3.86	1.29	1178,5	Dark Orange
7	901	0	5.23	1.74	1178.3	Green

3.2 OUTFOX

The major goal of Elcogen in the OUTFOX project is to demonstrate beyond state-of-the-art H₂ production capacity through components R&D, starting from unit cell level.

The first part of the project aims at assessing such improvements at short stack level, then gradually scaling up until reaching an 80 kW demonstrator where next generation components will be used. In this phase of the project, initial screening is done on standard

components and stacks, where 2 identical elcoStack® E350 are tested under similar conditions but different nominal current density. Initial polarization data are shown in Figure 3 for Stack #1 and Stack #2.

For Stack#1, the polarization test is performed up to 65 A, subsequently the stack is set for long term test at 60.5 A (equaling to 0.5 A/cm²). Stack #2 on the other hand is brought up to approx. 103 A (equaling to 0.85 A/cm²). Long-term test continues with similar setpoint. Both stacks have otherwise identical controlling parameters as described in the caption of Figure 3. The difference between the two curves arises from the fact that the Reactant Utilization (RU) is set to be 66% at the NOC, thus Stack#2 RU is lower than Stack#1 until the 103 A is reached.

Figure 3 Polarization curves of two elcoStack® E350 in SOE mode. Stack #1 was used for long term testing at 0.5 A/cm² while Stack #2 was used for long term testing at 0.85 A/cm².

Both stacks have 66% RU at nominal loading conditions, 40% H₂ flush, T_{gas,in}= 650°C

The comparison of the long term performance of the two stacks is depicted in Figure 4. Here the difference in voltage (dV) between the two stacks is plotted. The voltage difference is calculated as per equation 1:

$$dV [mV] = \bar{V}_{103A} [mV] - \bar{V}_{60.5A} [mV] \quad (\text{Eq.1})$$

Where \bar{V}_{103A} is the average cell voltage of Stack#2, operating at 0.85 A/cm² and $\bar{V}_{60.5A}$ is the average cell voltage of Stack#1, operating at 0.5 A/cm².

The initial voltage difference well corresponds to the value measured during the polarization curve. As the test progresses, the gap between the two stacks becomes wider, reaching up to almost 100 mV. This is due to the faster initial deactivation occurring in Stack#2, driven by the significantly higher current density.

At approximately 1000h, this phenomenon saturates as both stacks reach their respective stabilization point. The lower voltage of Stack#2 after the test unit maintenance break is likely due to the fact that the stack was cycled between SOE and SOFC mode, which potentially contributed to mitigating the initial deactivation. As Stack#2 test is currently

ongoing, additional information will be collected aimed at benchmarking how the two stacks will behave in the long run.

Figure 4 Voltage difference evolution of Stack#1 and Stack#2 under long term steam electrolysis.

4. Conclusions and Future Outlooks

Elcogen is committed to push its technology beyond the current state of the art for SO. This commitment is showcased in several projects which cover both FC and EL operation, tackling relevant topics such as fuel flexibility, high H₂ production and ease of modularity.

Remarkable fuel flexibility and robustness has been demonstrated within FuelSOME, where in this paper examples of tolerance against NH₃ slip have been demonstrated, where the stack withstood up to 15% NH₃. In the near future, such findings will be used in a 6kW stack module, showcasing the potential for this technology to decarbonize deep-sea shipping.

Similarly, the same stack platform enabled to reach a remarkable current density of 0.85 A/cm², marking a significant step forward compared to the current state of the art of 0.5 A/cm². The next step in the OUTFOX project will aim at further developing the electrochemical cell, striving to close the gap in voltage and bringing high current density closer to thermoneutral operation. Such findings, implemented first at short stack level, will be later on scaled up to full scale stacks and to a multi stack system which will stem as a key example of efficient and low-cost hydrogen production.

Acknowledgments

This work has been supported by the Clean Hydrogen Partnership. Co-funded by the European Union under Grant Agreements no. 101101439, 101006667, 101069828.

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Keywords: EFCF2024, Solid Oxide Technologies, SOC, Fuel Cells, SOFC, Electrolysers, SOE, Stack, Module, Fuel Flexibility